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AWARENESS, KNOWLEDGE AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES AGAINST LASSA FEVER AMONG RESIDENTS IN CALABAR METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

This study was aimed at assessing the awareness, knowledge and preventive measures against Lassa fever among residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to determine; awareness level of Lassa fever, knowledge level about Lassa fever, preventive practices against Lassa fever and attitude of residents in Calabar Metropolis towards preventive practices against Lassa fever. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was adopted for the study. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to randomly select 300 study participants for the study. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire and thereafter, information generated were synthesized, coded and entered into the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Results were expressed in simple percentages and presented in tables and charts. The results obtained in this study showed that 225 (75.0%) respondents indicated that they have heard of Lassa fever of which health worker 88 (39.1%) was their main source of information. Most respondents 150 (53.3%) recorded poor knowledge of Lassa fever. Preventive practices against Lassa fever as highlighted by the respondents included; clearing bushes 123 (54.7%), proper covering and storage of food/food items 89 (39.6%) and blocking holes around the house 41 (18.2%). Most respondents 258 (86.0%) exhibited positive attitude towards Lassa fever while the remaining 42 (14.0%) demonstrated negative attitude. It is recommended that public health experts and health

educators should liaise with community health workers to sensitize their community on emerging and re-emerging health issues (including Lassa fever). This would provide the platform for community members to access correct information about Lassa fever.

KEYWORDS: Lassa fever, knowledge, Preventive Practices, Attitude

INTRODUCTION

Lassa fever also known as Lassa Hemorrhagic Fever (LHF) is a type of viral hemorrhagic fever caused by the Lassa virus. Though first described in the 1950s, the virus was first identified in 1969 from a case in Lassa village, Borno State, Northern Nigeria. The illness is named after the town (Lassa) in Nigeria where the first cases occurred. The Lassa virus is a single stranded RNA virus, a member of the virus family Arenaviridae. The virus is zoonotic in that it spreads to man from rodents specifically multimammate rats (*Mastomys natalensis*) according to World Health Organization [WHO] (2019). According to Centre for Disease Control (2019), the infection is endemic in West African Countries (where the multimammate rats is common) and causes 300,000-500,000 cases annually with approximately 5,000 deaths. Outbreak of the disease has been observed in Nigeria (in all states), Liberia (mostly in Lofa & Nimbi countries), Sierra Leone (typically from Kenema and Kailahun districts) Guinea (Kinda, Faranah, & Nzerekore regions), but it is believed that human infections also exist in Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mali and Senegal (Ogbu, Ajuluchukwu, & Uneke, 2007).

The reservoir of Lassa virus are rodents of the genus *Mastomys natalensis*, commonly known as “multimammate rats” (rats with many breasts). The rat is indigenous to most of the Sub-Saharan region in African. It is probably the most common rodents in equatorial African, ubiquitous in human households and eaten as a delicacy in some areas (Fichet-Calvet & Rogers, 2009). Although the multimammate rat (*Mastomys natalensis*) is widely regarded as the reservoir of infection, *Mastomys erythroleucus* and *Mastomys hildbrandtii* have also known to be reservoirs (Anyanwu & Nwaopara, 2005).

According to Ochei, Abjejegah, Okoh & Abah (2014), *Mastomys* infected with Lassa virus do not become ill but they are able to shed the virus in their urine and feces which can be aerosolized, when symptoms occur they typically include fever, weakness, headaches, vomiting, muscle pains and less commonly there may be bleeding from the mouth or gastrointestinal tract.

According to the Centre for Disease Control (2019), Lassa fever is transmitted through animal to human. Transmission of the Virus is through contact with objects or materials with excretions or secretions of the virus deposited on the surfaces such as bed, floors etc. similarly, eating food or drinking water contaminated with feces or urine of an infected multimammate rat, contact with open wounds, preparing the infected multimammate rat (meat of wild or non-domesticated animals called bush meat or wild meat often prized as delicacy). According to Adewuyi, Fowotade & Adewuyi (2009), inhalation of infectious tiny particle (aerosol), is believed to be the most significant means of exposure. The virus cannot be spread through casual contact including skin to skin contact without exchange of body fluids, human to human transmission occurs through contact with the virus in the blood, urine, feces, and other bodily secretion of infected person with Lassa virus (Kelly, Barrie, Ross, Temple, and Moses & Bausch 2013).

As reported by CDC (2019), person to person transmission occurs in both community and healthcare facility (called nosocomial transmission) where Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) is not available or not used, Lassa virus may be spread in contaminated medical equipment such as re-used needles.

The Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) (2019), averred that the incubation period of the infection is 6-21 days after contact with Lassa fever; it is a severe hemorrhagic fever that present with general fever, malaise, headache, sore throat, muscle pain, chest pain, nausea, vomiting and diarrhea, cough, abdominal pain with or without bleeding. Clinically Lassa fever infectious is difficult to distinguish from other virus hemorrhagic fever such Ebola and Marburg, and from more common febrile illnesses such as malaria because the symptoms of Lassa fever are so varied and non-specified (Victor & Nwadiaro 2016). Signs and symptoms of Lassa fever typically manifest 1-3 weeks after the patient comes in contact with the virus. For majority of Lassa virus infections (approximately 80%) symptoms are mild and are undiagnosed (Asogun, Adomeh, Ehimuan, Hass, Gabrie,& Ehiane 2012). According to Masteer, et al Huang, Shehu & Paessler (2018), neurological problems have also been reported such as hearing loss, tremors and encephalitis death may occur within two weeks after symptom onset due to multi-organ failure, the most common complication of Lassa fever is deafness. The death rates of women in the third trimester pregnancy are particularly high and spontaneous abortion is a serious complication infection with an estimated 95% mortality in fetuses of infected pregnant mothers (CDC, 2019).

According to WHO (2019), the prevention of Lassa fever relies on promoting good “community hygiene” to discourage rodents from entering home. Effective measure includes storing grain and other foodstuffs in rodent- proof containers, regular hand washing, disposing of garbage far from the home, maintaining clean households. According to CDC (2018), because *Mastomys* are so abundant in endemic areas, it is not possible to completely eliminate them from the environment. Family members should always be careful to avoid contact with blood and bloody fluids while caring for sick. The disease occurs throughout the year, but more cases recorded during the dry season.

- **Statement of the problem**

Despite much global efforts through advances in research, and updated clinical management guidelines, Lassa fever continues to be a cause of mortality and morbidity in humans worldwide. Lassa fever is one of the infectious diseases that have a significant burden on public health and economic stability of societies in the entire world (Nii-Trebi, 2017). An estimated 100,000 to 300,000 infections occur annually, with approximately 5,000 deaths. Unfortunately, such estimates are crude because surveillance for disease is not uniformly performed. The disease is endemic in most West African countries with outbreaks occurring in Nigeria, Liberia, Guinea and Sierra Leone. In some areas of Sierra Leone and Liberia; it is known that 10%-16% of people admitted to hospitals have Lassa fever, which indicates the serious impact of the disease on the population of this regions and result in significant losses (CDC, 2019). The population at risk in Sierra Leone, Guinea and Nigeria may be as high as 59 million, with an annual incidence of illness of 3 million, and mortality as high as 67,000 (Adebayo, Nwobi, Vincent & Gonzalez, 2015).

As reported by CDC (2019), approximately 15%-20% of patients hospitalized for Lassa virus die from the illness and only 1% of all Lassa fever cases result in death but during epidemics the mortality can climb as high as 50%.

Among those who survive about a quarter has deafness which improves over time in about half. The death rates are particularly high for women in their third trimester of pregnancy, and for fetuses, about 95% of which die in the uterus of infected pregnant mothers. Presently there are no vaccines or antiviral drugs specifically approved for Lassa fever. Hence being a highly contagious disease with signs and symptoms similar to other endemic diseases, the creation of awareness on Lassa fever among residents in an unhygienic area such as those in Calabar Metropolis cannot be overemphasize. This will boost their knowledge and improve their attitude, thereby serving as a catalyst to drive adherence to preventive practices. The study therefore seeks to assess the awareness, knowledge and preventive practices against Lassa fever among residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study setting**

The setting for this study was Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State. Also known as the Canaan City, Calabar Metropolis is the Capital city of Cross River State, one of the States that makes up the South-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The City is adjacent to the Great Kwa River and creeks of the Cross River Basin. With an area of 406 square kilometers, it has a population of 371,022 inhabitants (2006 National census) and a projected population of 501,400 by 2016. Calabar Metropolis is made up of a total of 22 wards, 10 from Calabar South LGA and 12 from Calabar Municipality.

There are three (3) major ethnic groups in Calabar Metropolis. These are the Efiks, Quas and Efuts ethnic groups. Though they have different languages, the common language of these people is Efik. The occupation of the people is generally fishing, farming, trading and a few civil servants. The major religion of the people is Christianity and a few Traditionalist and Muslim. The main festival of the people is Christmas, Easter and New Year festivals.

- **Scope of the study**

This study focused on the awareness, knowledge and preventive practices against Lassa fever in Calabar Metropolis. The study was restricted to adults (18 years and above) residing in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

- **Study design**

This study utilized a cross-sectional descriptive study design.

- **Study population**

The study population consisted of both male and female adult residents in Calabar Metropolis.

- **Sample size determination**

The sample size for this study was determined using Bluman's formula (2004) (Cited by Ejemot-Nwadiaro, 2009)

The formula stated thus;

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where n = desired sample size

Z = the reliability coefficient for 95% confidence level = 1.96

P = proportion of occurrence = 21% (CDC, 2019)

q = proportion of non-occurrence, $(1-p)$

d = precision required 5%

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, } n &= \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.21 \times 0.79}{0.0025} \\ &= \frac{38416 \times 0.1659}{0.0025} \\ &= \frac{0.6373}{0.0025} \\ &= 255 \end{aligned}$$

To account for non-response rate of 15%

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence, } n &= \frac{n}{1 - \text{NRR}} \\ &= \frac{255}{1 - 0.15} \\ &= \frac{255}{0.85} \\ n &= 300 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, Sample size = 300

- **Sampling procedure**

A multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted for this study.

Stage 1: Selection of Wards

A total of 10 wards were selected from the 22 wards in Calabar Metropolis using simple random sampling technique. This was done using the lottery method. All the wards (12 wards) in Calabar South were written on pieces of papers, folded and placed into a basket and shaken vigorously. Five (5) folded papers were picked from the basket and these represented the selected ward. The same was done for Calabar Municipality as 5 wards was also selected.

Stage 2: Selection of streets

From the 10 wards selected, 3 streets were randomly selected from each of these wards to give a total of 30 streets. Here, streets in each of the wards were numbered. These numbers were written on piece of papers, fold, and place into a basket. After this, the folded papers in the basket were thoroughly shaken to mix properly; and then the researcher picked 3 papers taking 1 at a time without replacement. The streets represented by the numbers in the picked papers were used for the study.

Stage 3: Selection of Households

In each of the selected streets, households were selected using systematic random sampling technique. Using a systematic sampling, 10 households were selected from each of the 30 selected streets giving a total of 300 households. This will be done by using a fixed interval and a random starting point to select households from the streets.

$$\text{Sample interval} = \frac{\text{Total no. of households in a street}}{\text{No. of compound to be sample}}$$

Stage 4: Selection of Respondents

The researcher selected one respondent from each of the household that meets the inclusion criteria.

- **Instrument for data collection**

The instrument utilized for this study was a semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of five (5) sections (A – E) with twenty-two (22) questions in all. Section A comprises the socio-demographic information of the respondents. Section B comprises the awareness of Lassa fever among residents. Section C comprises the knowledge of Lassa fever among residents. Section D comprises the preventive practices against Lassa fever while section E comprises the attitude of resident towards Lassa fever.

- **Pre-testing**

A pre-test was carried out in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, and a city similar in characteristics to the study area. This was done using 10% of the sample size of this study in order to test the reliability and validity of the study instrument. However, the result of this test was not included in this work as it was also used to ascertain consistency of the research.

- **Data collection procedure**

The researcher first recruited and trained two research assistants to aid in the data collection process. Data was obtained using a semi-structured questionnaire which was self-administered and interviewer-administered questionnaire.

- **Method of data analysis**

Data collected using the questionnaire were coded and entered into the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Data analyzed were presented using table, percentages and charts. To determine the knowledge of respondents about Lassa fever, a suitable scoring system was used where each correct option was scored 1 while an incorrect option was scored 0. The average of the total correct scores was used as the index score to measure the knowledge level of respondents. After the computation, respondents who indicated the correct options (at least above the average score) were classified as those who demonstrated good knowledge while those who indicated the wrong options (below the average score) were categorized as those that exhibited poor knowledge. To determine attitude of respondents towards lassa fever, 5- point Likert scale scoring system was

used which include; Strongly agree=4, Agree=3, Disagree=2, Strongly disagree=1 and 0=I don't know, for positively worded questions. While 0=I don't know, Strongly Agree=1, Agree=2, Disagree=3 and strongly disagree=4 was for negatively worded questions. Mean score was derived from the scoring system as follows;

Mean score = sum of individual score/number of scores = $4+3+2+1+0/4 = 10/4 = 2.5$

Hence, the mean score obtained was 2.5. Respondents who had a mean score of 2.5 and above were adjudged to have exhibited positive attitude towards lassa fever while those whose mean score was below 2.5 were categorized as those who demonstrated negative attitude.

- **Ethical consideration**

A letter of introduction and ethical clearance was obtained from the Department of Public Health Ethical Committee, University of Calabar. This letter was presented to the Community leaders for approval before the commencement of data collection. The purpose, general content and nature of the investigation was explained to respondents to obtain their consent before inclusion into the study and assured of confidentiality of the information they provide as their names, contact, and address were included in the questionnaire. Also, participants were informed that participation was voluntary and anonymity will be kept and they are free to opt out at any point in time.

RESULTS

This focuses on the analysis and presentation of data collected for the study. Using self administered and interviewer administered method of data collection, the researcher administered three hundred (300) questionnaires and same were collected giving a response rate of 100%. These questionnaires were sorted by the researcher, and data obtained were analyzed and presented using frequency tables, charts, frequency counts and simple percentages.

- **Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents**

As showed in table 1, the highest number of respondents were those in the age bracket of 28-32 years, with 91(30.3%) , this was followed closely by those aged 23-27 years, 89(29.7%). There were 55(18.3%), 34(11.3%) and 31(10.3%) respondents aged between 37 years and above, 33-37 and 18-22 years respectively. There were more females, 166(55.3%) than males, 134(44.7%).

Analysis of the marital status revealed that majority of the respondents 162 (54.0%) were married, 112(37.3%) were single and 18(6.0%) cohabiting. About 4(1.3%) and 2(0.7%), of the respondents were widowed and divorced respectively in the study. Majority of the respondents had tertiary education, 78 (26.0%), while 10 (3.3) had no formal education. The main occupations were civil servants 78(26.0%), followed by trading 71(23.7%).

Christianity was the dominant religion, 285(95.0%), followed by Islamic religion, 12(4.0%), and about 3(1.0%) respondents was traditional religion adherents.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents (n=300)

Variables	Number of respondents	Percentage
Age (in years)		
18-22	31	10.3
23-27	89	29.7
28-32	91	30.3
33-37	34	11.3
37 and above	55	18.3
Sex		
Male	134	44.7
Female	166	55.3
Marital status		
Single	112	37.3
Married	162	54.0
Widow/Widower	4	1.3
Divorced	2	0.7
Separated	2	0.7
Cohabiting	18	6.0
Education		
No formal education	10	3.3
Primary	36	12.0
Secondary	126	42.0
Tertiary	128	42.7
Occupation		
Student	61	20.3
Farming	35	11.7
Trading	71	23.7
Artisan	55	18.3
Civil servant	78	26.0
Religion		
Christianity	285	95.0
Islam	12	4.0
Traditional religion	3	1.0

- **Awareness of Lassa fever among respondents**

Results as indicated in table 2 shows that 225 (75.0%) of the respondents indicated that they have heard of Lassa fever health worker 88 (39.1%), radio/Television 78 (34.7%) and book/magazine 32 (14.2%) were their major sources of information on Lassa fever respectively.

Table 2: Awareness of Lassa fever among respondents

Variables	Number of respondents	Percentage
Ever heard of Lassa fever		
Have heard	225	75.0
Have not heard	75	25.0
Total	300	100
Source of information on Lassa fever*		
Health worker	88	39.1
Radio/Television	78	34.7
Newsprint	15	6.7
Billboards/fliers	12	5.3
Friends/relatives	18	8.0
Book/magazine	32	14.2

*Multiple responses

- **Knowledge about Lassa fever among respondents**

Results on knowledge of Lassa fever among respondents showed that 104 (46.2%) knew the causative agent of Lassa fever while 121(53%) do not have knowledge about the causative agent of Lassa fever, of which 55 (52.9%) identified virus as the causative agent of Lassa fever. While 145 (64.4%) respondents identified rats as the main animal species that transmit Lassa fever virus to humans, mode of transmission of Lassa fever as indicated by the respondents were mainly; through direct contact with blood, urine, feces and other bodily secretion of an infected patient 88 (39.1%), consuming contaminated food with infected rat 67 (29.8%) eating poorly cooked rats 45 (20.0%) and inhaling infected air 41(18.2%). Most of the respondents identified fever 113(50.2%) as the major symptoms of Lassa fever, followed by bleeding 56(24.9%). Majority of the respondents 201(89.3%) indicated that Lassa fever can be prevented while 24(10.7%) indicated that Lassa fever cannot be prevented. (Table3). Prevention of Lassa fever as indicated by the respondents were mainly; maintaining a clean environment 92 (40.9%), keeping food in tightly closed containers 81 (36.0%) and wearing protective clothing such as face mask and hand gloves 56 (24.9%). A reasonable proportion of the respondents 121 (53.8%) affirmed that they have knowledge of symptoms of Lassa fever of which fever 113 (50.2%), bleeding 56 (24.9%) and swelling of the face 51 (22.7%) were the most highlighted. Most respondents 201 (89.3%) acknowledge that Lassa fever can be prevented (Table 3).

On the average, 140 (46.7%) recorded good knowledge of Lassa fever while the remaining 160 (53.3%) recorded poor knowledge (Figure 1).

Table 3: Knowledge about Lassa fever among respondents

Variables	Number of respondents	Percentage
Have knowledge of causative agent of Lassa fever		
Had knowledge	104	46.2
Do not have knowledge	121	53.8
Total	225	100
Causative agent of Lassa fever		
Bacteria	21	20.2
Virus	55	52.9
Fungi	28	26.9
Total	104	100
Animal species that transmit Lassa fever virus to human		
Do not know	20	8.9
Rats	145	64.4
Bats	25	11.1
Monkeys	35	15.6
Total	225	100
Mode of transmission of Lassa fever*		
Do not know	18	8.0
Consuming contaminated food with infected rat	67	29.8
Direct contact with blood, urine, feces and other bodily secretion of an infected patient	88	39.1
Eating poorly cooked rats	45	20.0
Inhaling infected air	41	18.2
Prevention of Lassa fever*		
Do not know	18	8.0
Keeping food in tightly closed containers	81	36.0
Wearing protective clothing such as face mask and hand gloves	56	24.9
Maintaining a clean environment	92	40.9
Sealing holes in the house	47	20.9
Have knowledge of symptoms of Lassa fever		
Had knowledge	121	53.8
Do not have knowledge	104	46.2
Total	225	100
Symptoms of Lassa fever		
Bleeding	56	24.9
Fever	113	50.2
Swelling of the face	51	22.7

Chest/back pain	47	20.9
Restlessness	36	16.0
Hearing loss	17	7.6
Knowledge that Lassa fever can be prevented		
Can be prevented	201	89.3
Cannot be prevented	24	10.7
Total	225	100

*Multiple responses

- **Preventive practices against Lassa fever among respondents**

Preventive practices against Lassa fever as indicated by the respondents included; clearing bushes 123 (41%), proper covering and storage of food/food items 89 (29.7%), keeping predators e.g cats 47 (15.7%) and blocking holes around the house 41 (18.2%) (Figure2).

Fig 2: Respondents' preventive practices against Lassa fever

- **Attitude of respondents towards Lassa fever**

As revealed in table 4, 31 (10.3%) strongly agree to the statement that there is no need to take preventive measures against Lassa fever because is not a serious illness, 34 (11.3%) agree, 105 (35.0%) disagree and 55 (18.3%) strongly disagree; 11 (3.7%) strongly agree to the statement that rats are very delicious for meals, 18 (6.0%) agree, 78 (26.0%) disagree and 18 (39.3%) strongly disagree; 160 (53.3%) strongly agree to the opinion that they hate to see rat in their house and 140 (46.7%) agree; 178 (59.3%) strongly agree to the opinion that they don't like eating left over foods that are not properly covered and 122 (40.7%) agree; 11 (3.7%) strongly agree to the statement that

they keep waste basket inside their houses, 21 (7.0%) agree, 112 (37.3%) disagree and 156 (52.0%) strongly disagree (Table 4).

Table 4: Attitude of respondents towards Lassa fever (n=300)

Variables	Strongly agree (%)	Agree (%)	I don't know (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly disagree (%)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no need to take preventive measures against Lassa fever because is not a serious illness 	31 (10.3)	34 (11.3)	75 (25.0)	105 (35.0)	55 (18.3)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rats are very delicious for meals 	11 (3.7)	18 (6.0)	75 (25.0)	78 (26.0)	18 (39.3)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I hate to see rat in my house 	160 (53.3)	140 (46.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I don't like eating left over foods that are not properly covered 	178 (59.3)	122 (40.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I keep waste basket inside my house 	11 (3.7)	21 (7.0)	0 (0.0)	112 (37.3)	156 (52.0)

On the average, 258 (86.0%) respondents exhibited positive attitude towards Lassa fever while the remaining 42 (14.0%) demonstrated negative attitude (Figure 3).

Fig 3: Respondents' attitude towards Lassa fever

DISCUSSION

Lassa fever has evolved from decades of Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) into a high priority pathogen which is gradually gaining international recognition (Annie, 2015). Due to its sporadic outbreaks across the western part of the African continent and its increasing prevalence in Nigeria, it became imperative to assess the awareness, knowledge, attitude and preventive practices against Lassa fever amongst the populace in the study area.

- **Awareness of Lassa fever by the respondents**

Findings from the study indicated that 225 (75.0%) of the respondents have heard of Lassa fever of which health worker 88 (39.1%), radio/Television 78 (34.7%) and book/magazine 32 (14.2%) were

their major sources of information (Table 2). This result is congruent with other studies in Nigeria where high awareness level of Lassa fever was documented (Ochei et al, 2014; Olayinka et al, 2015; Reuben et al, 2016; Sagir et al, 2019). The high level of awareness of Lassa fever recorded in the current study may be attributed to improved access to health information especially during outbreaks. It is a common observation that after a typical outbreak of disease such as Lassa fever, information is usually disseminated via the electronic media (radio/television) to reach a significant proportion of the population with the aim of mitigating the spread. Simultaneously, infected cases are taken to the health care facility for prompt treatment from which information are disseminated to other health care facilities across the country so that health care providers can adopt preventive measures to avoid being infected with the virus. In some communities, community volunteers in collaboration with facility-based service providers sensitize their surrounding communities on the danger of Lassa fever and its preventive strategies. This may largely account for why the health workers and electronic media were their top sources of information on Lassa fever.

- **Knowledge about Lassa fever amongst respondents**

As regards knowledge of Lassa fever, more than half of the respondents 160 (53.3%) recorded poor knowledge of Lassa fevers (Figure 1). This finding corroborates with other Nigerian studies where a significant proportion of the respondents lack knowledge of Lassa fever (Tobin, et al, 2010; Adebimpe, 2015; Sagir et al, 2019), but disagrees with Rueben et al (2016) where high knowledge of Lassa fever was reported. Poor access to information on Lassa fever, minimal outbreaks of Lassa fever in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria and low reported cases in Calabar metropolis could significantly account for the lack of knowledge about Lassa fever demonstrated in the current study. On the other hand, it is possible that the 140 (46.7%) respondents who recorded good knowledge of Lassa fever may largely be health workers or medical students who expectedly should have access to information on Lassa fever. Knowledge of an infected person and personal effort of respondents to understand the mode of transmission, sign and symptoms as well as preventive measures of Lassa fever could also account for their knowledge level.

- **Preventive practices against Lassa fever**

Preventive practices against Lassa fever as indicated by the respondents included; clearing bushes especially around residential homes, proper covering and storage of food/food items, keeping predator's e.g cats and blocking holes around the house (Figure 2). The results showed that respondents acknowledge the importance of environmental hygiene and its impact on physical health

and wellbeing. These findings are in accordance with that of CDC (2018) and FMOH (2019) where a number of preventive strategies against Lassa fever were highlighted which include; avoiding contact with infected persons whether alive or dead, avoiding spreading food items along roadsides and open spaces, discarding all food particles eaten by rats or other animals, avoid the eating of rats and avoiding the drinking or touching water used to bath dead bodies. Efforts should be geared towards creating an unfriendly environment for rodents to operate and thrive. This can be achieved by promoting community hygiene, storing grain and other foodstuffs in rodent- proof containers, regular hand washing, disposing of garbage far from the home and maintaining clean households as opined by WHO (2019). Adopting the aforementioned preventive measures is primarily to mitigate Lassa fever spread among the populace.

- **Attitude towards preventive practices against Lassa fever by the respondents**

Based on attitude of respondents towards Lassa fever, 258 (86.0%) respondents exhibited positive attitude towards Lassa fever while the remaining 42 (14.0%) demonstrated negative attitude (Figure 3). High positivity was largely shown in statements regarding high-risk perception of Lassa fever, improved environmental hygiene and proper storage of solid waste to avoid the infestation of rodents (Table 4). This finding agrees with that of Ighedosa et al (2016) where most study participants recorded excellent attitude towards Lassa fever. The high positive attitude towards Lassa fever demonstrated in the current study may be linked to the desire of respondents to stay healthy by avoiding the activities, practices or lifestyles that may initiate or instigate outbreak of Lassa fever in their surroundings.

CONCLUSION

Lassa fever is an emerging infectious disease that is currently gaining attention globally. Outbreaks of the disease have been widely observed in Nigeria. Preventing the spread of Lassa fever is largely infringed in the level of awareness, knowledge and preventive practices adopted by the populace. Findings in this study showed that awareness level of Lassa fever was high but respondents lack knowledge of the intricacies of Lassa fever with regards to mode of transmission, symptoms and preventive practices. Also, respondents demonstrated excellent preventive practices against Lassa fever and positive attitude towards Lassa fever. Hence, efforts should be geared towards sensitizing the populace about the intricacies of Lassa fever.

- **Recommendations**

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations were made;

- Public health experts and health educators should liaise with community health workers to sensitize their community on emerging and re-emerging health issues (including Lassa fever). This would provide the platform for community members to access correct information about Lassa fever and raise the consciousness of Lassa fever outbreaks.
- Information about Lassa fever outbreaks and spread should always be disseminated via the electronic media (radio/TV) since it was one of the major sources of information recorded in the current study.
- In communities and cultures where consumption of rats is highly encouraged, community health workers should sensitize such communities on the health implications of such practices.
- Further studies should be conducted and tailored at assessing knowledge, attitude and preventive practices against Lassa fever among pregnant women since they are often regarded as one of the vulnerable populations of Lassa fever.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, D., Nwobi, E. A., Vincent, T., Gonzalez, J. P.(2015). Response Preparedness to Viral Hemorrhagic Fever in Nigeria: risk perception, attitude towards Lassa fever. *Epidemiology (Sunnyvale)*, 5(199), 2161-1165
- Adebimpe, W. O. (2015). Community awareness and perception towards rodents control: Implications for prevention and control of Lassa fever in urban slums of south western Nigeria, *Research Journal of Health Sciences*, 4(3), 26-32
- Adefisan, A. K. (2014). The level of Awareness that Rat is a vector of Lassa fever among the rural people in Ijebu-North Local Government, Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5, (37), 166-17
- Adewuyi, G. M., Fowotade, A., & Adewuyi, B. T. (2009). Lassa fever: another infectious menace. *African Journal of Clinical and Experimental Microbiology*, 10(3).

- Akhuemokhan, O. C., Ewah-Odiase, R. O., Akpede, N., Ehimuan, J., Adomeh, D. I., Odia, I., & Asogun, D. A. (2017). Prevalence of Lassa Virus Disease (LVD) in Nigerian Children with fever or fever and convulsions in an endemic area. *Public Library of Science neglected tropical diseases*, 11(7), e0005711.
- Amorosa, V., MacNeil, A., McConnell, R., Patel, A., Dillon, KE., Hamilton, K., Erickson, BR., Campbell, S., Knust, B., Cnon, D., Miller, D., Manning, C., Rollin, PE., & Nichol, ST. (2010). Imported Lassa fever, Pennsylvania, USA. *Emergency Infectious Disease journal*.16, (10), 1598-600.
- Annie, W. (2015). Lassa fever: The politics of an emerging disease and the scope for one's health. Retrieved August 25, from <http://googlesearch/mediaandlassafever.com>.
- Anuforo, E. (2016). Waging a war against Lassa fever. *Guardian Newspaper*, January 11th.
- Anyanwu, R. A., & Nwaopara, A. O., (2005). Effects of care education on timeliness and completeness of routine immunization: An assessment in rural communities in North – central Nigeria. *International journal of community research*, 3 (3), 2384-6828.
- Asogun, D. A., Adomeh, D. I., Ehimuan, J., Odia, I., Hass, M., Gabriel, M., & Ehiane, P. E. (2012). Molecular diagnostics for Lassa fever at Irrua specialist teaching hospital, Nigeria: lessons learnt from two years of laboratory operation. *Public Library of Science neglected tropical diseases*, 6(9), e839.
- Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2018). Lassa fever, signs and symptoms. *Division of High-Consequences Pathogens and Pathology (DHCPP)*. Atlanta, Georgia
- Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2019). Lassa fever. *National Centre for emerging and zoonotic disease*. Atlanta, Georgia.
- Durojaje, A., Amaechi, E., Tom, V. & Jean-Paul, G. (2015). Response preparedness to viral Hemorrhagic fever in Nigeria: Risk Perception, Attitude towards Lassa fever. Retrieved August 25, from <http://googlesearch/lasafeverawarenessc.com>.
- Ejemot-Nwadiaro, R. I. (2009). *A guide to Biostatistics and Health Research methods*, Sample size determination. Calabar, Datapro Publishers.

Federal Ministry of Health, (2019). What you need to know about Lassa fever. Flier, retrieved from <http://www.ncdc.gov.ng>

Fichet-Calvet, E., & Rogers, D. J. (2009). Risk maps of Lassa fever in West Africa. *Public Library of Science neglected tropical diseases*, 3(3), e388.

Ighedosa, U, S., Odigie, E, A., Usifoh, F, S., Asemota, O., Asemota, O, D., & Aighewi T, I. (2016) Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Lassa fever Prevention. *Journal of Science and Practice of Pharmacy*, 3(1), 75-83.

Kelly, J. D., Barrie, M. B., Ross, R. A., Temple, B. A., Moses, L. M., & Bausch, D. G. (2013). Housing equity for health equity: a rights-based approach to the control of Lassa fever in post-war Sierra Leone. *Business Model Canvas international health and human rights*, 13(1), 2.

Laura, A. K., Bjorn, S. H., Imran, E. & Deeann M. R. (2016). *Bush meat and emerging infectious diseases: lessons from Africa*. Switzerland: Springer international publishing.

Lucas, A. O. & Gilles, H. M. (2010). *A New Short Textbook of Preventive Medicine for the Tropics*, (3rd edition) Singapore: Colset Private Ltd.

Mateer, E. J., Huang, C., Shehu, N. Y., & Paessler, S. (2018). Lassa fever–induced sensor neural hearing loss: A neglected public health and social burden. *Public Library of Science neglected tropical diseases*, 12(2), e0006187.

Nii-Trebi, N. I. (2017). Emerging and neglected infectious diseases: insights, advances, and challenges. *Biomedical research international*, 1(1), 56.

Ochei, O, Abejegah, C, Okoh, E, & Abah, S. O (2014). Housing Factors and Transmission of Lassa fever in West African sub-region: an overview. *Journal of vector borne disease*, 44(1), 1.

Ogbu, O., Ajuluchukwu, E., & Uneke, C. J. (2007). Lassa fever in West African sub-region: an overview. *Journal of vector borne diseases*, 44(1), 1.

Olanyinka, S I., Bridget, O. Faith O, A., & Peter, A., (2015). Awareness of Lassa fever in a Rural Community in South West Nigeria. *Journal of Community Health Research*, 4(1), 1-10.

Olayemi, A., Cadar, D., Magassouba, N. F., Obadare, A., Kourouma, F., Oyeyiola, A., ... & Jérôme, H. (2016). New hosts of the Lassa virus. *Scientific reports*, 6, 25280.

- Rueben C. R. & Gyar. S. D. (2016). Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Lassa fever in and Around Lafia, Central Nigeria. *International Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology Research*, 2 (1), 014-019.
- Sagir, A & Ahmed S, M. (2019) Assessment of Knowledge of Lassa fever Among Residents in North-Eastern Nigeria, *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 9(2), 4 -6
- Sheriff, B. (2015). Lassa fever awareness campaign. Retrieved August 25, from <http://googlesearch/lassafeverawarenessmedia.com>
- Tobin, E. A., Asogun, D. A., Isah, E. C. & Ugege, O. G. (2013). Assessment of knowledge and attitude towards Lassa fever among primary health care providers in an endemic suburban community of Edo State: Implications for control. *Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 4(8), 311-318.
- Ugochukwu, N. S., & Agatha, O. E. (2017) The Fight against Lassa fever in Ebonyi State, Nigeria: A Clash of the People's Culture and Broadcast Media Campaign. *International Digital Organization for Scientific Research Journal of Communication and English*, (1), 159-180
- Victor, K. & Nwadiaro, E. C. (2016). Lassa fever: focus medical/academic research and popular press depiction. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*. 4(7):29-36
- Wogu, J. O., Chukwu, C. O., Nwafor, K. A., Anikpe, E. A., Ugwuoke, J. C., Ugwulor-Onyinyechi, C. C., & Eseadi, C. (2019). Mass media reportage of Lassa fever in Nigeria: a viewpoint. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 3(6), 51-55.
- World Health Organization (2019). Lassa fever WHO. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/Lassa-fever>